

Supplementary data and figures

Related to the manuscript submitted to *Holzforschung* journal in July, 2020

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Title: **Treatment of wood with atmospheric plasma discharge: Study of the treatment process, dynamic wettability and interactions with a waterborne coating**

Research part: *Results and discussion - Discharge intensity and plasma streamers distribution*

Figure S1: Enlarged photos of the samples, exposed to plasma discharges. Above each particular photo there are stated the normal density and moisture content of material.

Figure S2: Overall comparison of distribution (thin lines) and average (thick lines) of detected light intensity, measured in the discharges.

Research part: Results and discussion – Coating penetration depth

Figure S3 Examples of beech and spruce wood segmentations, including the percentage of non-air voxels. The scale bar represents 500 μm .